

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF INTONATION IN THE EXPRESSION OF MODAL-EMOTIONAL ATTITUDES

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Abstract

Depending on the unique features of the phonetic structure of each language, their intonation also differs from each other. The concept of pronunciation norms of the language includes intonation and its components. Intonation not only puts sentences into certain forms, but also divides them into meaning units - syntagms in order to make the ideas expressed in the sentences understandable. Foreign linguists also note that it is necessary to pay a lot of attention to sentence stress and melody in speech. Intonation not only organizes sentences, but also determines their communicative types, marks connections between sentences, expresses modal emotional relationships. Intonation is the main leading tool in living speech.

Keywords: intonation, modal, melody, tempo, pause, phonology

Intonation, which forms the meaning of sentences, strengthens it, and even subverts the meaning of the sentence, has a certain form. Intonation is the heart of a sentence. R.Kingdon notes that if the phoneme system of the language constitutes the dry "skeleton" of words and sentences, intonation constitutes its "soul", "body" (1, p. 76). In addition to organizing sentences, intonation determines their communicative type, shows the structural type of sentences, reveals the presence of additional elements within the sentence, notes the strength and weakness of meaning connections between sentences and syntagms, gives emphasis to words in sentences, expresses contrast, modal-emotional relations.

Intonation has a semantic character as a language phenomenon. Intonation, as a linguistic and communicative sign, can distinguish one sentence from another.

In linguistics, the concept of intonation is explained in two ways - narrow and broad. In foreign linguistics, the concept of intonation is identified with the concept of melody. English linguists separate melody and sentence stress and explain them as separate phonetic-phonological phenomena. A. Gimson interprets intonation as changes in tone, i.e. rises and falls in the level of the tone. He especially emphasizes the fact that different degrees of stress in a sentence can be signaled through intonation (2, p. 75). D. Crystal includes the change of tone of voice, intensity-loudness, rhythmicity in intonation (3, p. 89). G.P. Torsuyev approaches intonation in a broad sense. He explains intonation as a complex combination of voice tone, intensity, timbre and tempo in speech and considers intonation the most important method of expressing the meaning of speech (4, p. 63).

D. Jones explains intonation as the change in tone of voice - rising and falling. He explains intonation as equivalent to changes in pitch. He notes that every sentence, every word, every syllable is given a tone of voice during a conversation. According to him, there is no sentence without tone (5, p. 96). Some linguists give the same explanation to intonation, or they do not explain it at all. However, all authors emphasize the im-

portance of a number of other factors, including sentence stress, rhythm, pause, etc. show, but do not include them in the concept of intonation.

V.A. Vasiliyev explains intonation as a combination of speech melody, sentence stress, sound quality (timbre) and speech tempo, and intonation allows the speaker to sufficiently express his opinion, desires and emotions, attitude to existence and the content of speech. According to him, rhythm is also included in the component of intonation (6, p. 21).

O. Dikushina equates intonation with speech melody. O. Dikushina explains intonation as special organizing facts of communicative speech. According to him, intonation consists of the following factors:

- 1) rhythmic and syntactical division of connected speech into syntagms.
- 2) sentence stress;
- 3) melodic models of different communicative types;
- 4) voice tone and accent signs that turn our speech into emphatic (7, p. 134).

S.M.Babayev and M.G.Garayeva explain intonation as a complex unity of all prosodic or suprasegmental elements of speech. According to them, the main prosodic elements are also called components of intonation. They note that the main components of intonation are speech melody, sentence stress, speech tempo and voice timbre. (8, p. 129).

The structure of intonation is different in different languages. The concept of expressing emotion or thought is more complex in itself. First, emotion can be expressed voluntarily or involuntarily. If the speaker says something happily, he probably feels happy or behaves as if he is happy. Second, the idea expressed can be an attitude towards the listener. There are different forms of pronunciation of a sentence. For example; She wants to go to the country.

This sentence can be said in a state of begging, bitterness, sadness, joy, and pride. At this time, there are changes in the loudness and speed of the sound. A sound occurs in a completely narrow range in tonal level, or in a wide range between the high and low pitch

of the sound. Having a voice in different ranges is similar to making different facial expressions, gestures and body movements during speech.

To know the relation of intonation to these factors, we can distinguish three types of suprasegmental change: segmental, prosodic and paralinguistic.

These components of intonation are observed in other elements that occur one after the other. prehead, scales, tones and tail, breaks, tone boundaries

Speech cannot exist without voice range, loudness, speed and timbre. Each person has these unique qualities. The encounters between prosodic components are related to the characteristics of speakers.

In paralinguistics, it can be noted from human facial expressions, gestures and body movements. People who study human behavior often use the phrase "body language" during such activities. There are also certain sound effects for laughing and coughing. These paralinguistic effects are evident in speech. Paralinguistic features of sound effect are treated as a part of intonation. D. Crystal notes that paralinguistic features are the physiological results of the vocal cords as a direct result of the processing of the pharynx, mouth and nose cavities. Some scientists include in the term paralinguistics the so-called prosody, that is, the expansion of the voice range, loudness, voice tempo and voice quality (3, p. 151).

The role of intonation and other prosodic tools in the formation of modality is very large. The role of intonation in speech intelligibility and understanding of meaning is very large. Unfortunately, the syntactic features of intonation have not been paid enough attention, and its linguistic essence has not been explained. One of the most important tasks of modern syntactic theory and text syntax should be considered a thorough investigation of the role of prosodic means in the language system and speech formation. Before clarifying the role of intonation and other prosodic devices in the formation of modality, it would be appropriate to explain some terms. The point is that it is possible to find different explanations of the same term in many literatures. Conditional signs are also different from each other. Tone - the rise and fall of the tone of the voice as a result of stretching the vocal cords. A rising tone is shown to indicate uncertainty. A rising tone can be marked as (<), a falling tone as (>), and a neutral tone as (-).

Rhythm is an important prosodic tool that regularly follows each other in the speech process of acceleration, deceleration, tension and weakness, length and brevity, etc.;

Intensity - strong and weak pronunciation of sounds, strength of voice. Stress - stronger and louder pronunciation of the syllables in the word and one of the words in the sentences. In our research, modal is understood as a different pronunciation of words and phrases for a more prominent expression of a certain idea;

Tempo - fast or slow expression of speech. This prosodic device can add a certain nuance of meaning to modal expressions;

Timbre - one of the various interpretations of this term is the addition of other tones (harmonic overtone

and resonator tone) to the main tone to obtain an expressive-emotional tone. Feelings of sadness, joy, anger, hatred, etc. are expressed by timbre in the speech process. The terms indicated in the study will be used in the meanings given. As is known, modality is characterized as a grammatical-semantic category that reflects the relationship of the speaker's expressed idea to the objective entity. The interlocutor's attitude to the said opinion can have different meanings. This variety can be expressed by shades of reality, unreality, possibility, impossibility, necessity, probability, etc. Prosodic means also play a leading role in the formation of these indicated meanings. It is not accidental that different types of intonation (informative intonation, question intonation, exclamation) are the most important means of expression of either objective or subjective modality.

Intonation expressing happiness, sadness, doubt, surprise, determination, disbelief, hesitation, sarcasm, etc.) is widely observed.

Low pre-head+Low fall+tail - This intonation structure conveys exhaustion, certainty, and absoluteness in declarative sentences.

Where is your brother?-At the office.

In this intonation structure special questions evoke a serious, restrained impression.

I have got a flat.- Where?

It is used in sentences expressing command to show emotionless, serious feelings.

It is my book.- Then take it.

It expresses calm and restrained feelings in exclamation sentences.

We have got no ear-phones.- Pity.

Low pre-head+descending head+low fall+tail- This group of melodies conveys a thought-out, absolute, complete idea in the sentences.

Have you any news of Tom?- We haven't heard from him for ages.

It serves to express seriousness and impatience in interrogative sentences especially, special questions.

Harry is not coming to tea- who is coming to tea, then?

In imperative sentences, it expresses harsh, serious, oppressive feelings and thoughts.

Here are the magazines.- don't put them all on my table.

Low pre-head+low rise+tail- This structure is used in the declarative sentences for non-absoluteness, incompleteness, transition to another idea and light judgement.

You know where Jack lives?- Yes.

It expresses a slight sense of surprise in special questions.

You must do it this way- how?

How old are you?- how old am I?

It expresses negative approach and skeptical opinions in imperative sentences.

They are arriving next week- Are they?

It expresses a mild warning in imperative sentences.

Teacher to class- Start. A gain. Stop.

This melody group is used in exclamatory sentences, mostly in greetings, and is usually used as an introduction to a conversation.

Good morning- , Morning.

Low pre-head+Descending head+Low rise+Tail- In declarative sentences, it expresses non-categorical and indicates incompleteness.

Shall I buy the TV-set?- → If you ' don't 'find it 'too , expensive.

In special questions it is used to express sympathy and interest.

Alice is on the phone- → Whom does she 'want to , speak to.

It took me four hours to do the exercise.- It took you 'four 'hours to 'do , what?

Ümümi sual cümlələrində marağ ifadə edir. It expresses interest in general questions.

Hope to see you some day.- → Will you in'vite me to your 'evening , party?

It is used to express insisting and encouragement in a command sentence.

I can't do it.- → Try it a ,gain.

It is used for encouraging purposes in exclamatory sentences and used in informal greetings.

Anything else?- No , thank you.

Low pre-head+Descending head+ Mid-level+Tail.- This intonation structure is used in incomplete intonation groups.

Shall call on you on Saturday?

-On >Sunday | Γ II be glad to , → see you.

Low pre-head+Fall rise+Tail This intonation structure is used to express reproach, contradiction in the declarative sentences.

Can you play chess?- , Once I ,could.

But you are not free on Sunday- , Usually I am ,not.

What do you think of my new suit-The , colour is all ,right

Conclusion. There are two approaches in linguistics based on the content of intonation: narrow and broad approach. English linguists D. Jones, R. Kingdon, A. Gimson, explain the concept of intonation as a change in tone of voice during speech. Russian Germanists G. Torsuyev V. Vasiliyev and Azerbaijani linguists A. Akhundov, S. Babayev, F. Veysalli approach the concept of intonation in a broad sense. They consider intonation as a phenomenon of suprasegmental composition with a complex composition consisting of melody, sentence stress, tempo, timbre, rhythm, pause. Intonation organizes sentences and determines their communicative types, such as interjections, author's words, direct addresses, and homogenous members. Its components are melody, sentence stress, tempo of speech, rhythm, timbre of voice. Melody is the main component of intonation, the fall and rise of voice tone. Melody serves to indicate the communicative type of the sentence more than other components of intonation. Timbre expresses different emotional shades in the speech process. Intonation plays a very important role in the expression of modal-emotional relationships and in the correct delivery of ideas to the listener.

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